

Call for proposals

Strengthening Local and Thematic DCCs

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1 Introduction

In this Call for proposals information is provided about the application procedure for the “Strengthening local and thematic DCCs” funding round. This Call for proposals falls under the responsibility of Open Science NL, part of the Dutch Research Council (NWO).

In this Call for proposals you will find information about the aim of this programme (Chapter 2), the conditions for the grant application (Chapter 3) and how your proposal will be assessed (Chapter 4). This is the information you need to submit a grant application. Chapter 5 states the obligations for grant recipients in the event you are awarded funding. Chapter 6 contains the contact details and Chapter 7 the annexes.

1.1 Background

The Dutch government has made available substantial funding to support the transition to open science in the Netherlands. The aim of the investment is to make open science the norm. A budget of €20M a year is available until 2031. Open Science NL was set up to take responsibility for the allocation of these funds. Open Science NL is part of NWO.

This call falls within the first work programme of Open Science NL, which covers the years 2024-2025. The instruments within this work programme cover the following priority areas:

1. Capacity building,
2. Infrastructure for Open Science,
3. Robust research processes,
4. Evidence base for Open Science,
5. Empowering communities.

This work programme addresses a comprehensive set of needs and range of areas relating to open science, and provides a strong basis from which the uptake of open science practices can continue to grow and flourish in the Netherlands.

The Call for Proposals “Strengthening local and thematic DCCs” falls under the priority area “Capacity building”. Investing in capacity building for open science is one of the essential requirements for putting open science into practice. Capacity building refers here to the process of enhancing the organisational or community-based knowledge, skills and abilities needed to adopt open science practices effectively. In other words, capacity building refers to investment in people and their skills. Capacity building initiatives provide much needed training and support to navigate the technical, legal, social, cultural and ethical aspects of open science, thereby enabling communities to overcome barriers and embrace new approaches. Ultimately, capacity building strengthens the foundations of sustainable open science ecosystems, which encompass not only specific research outputs (publications, data, software and non-traditional research output, such as creative works, policy reports, etc.), but also research processes, infrastructures and research cultures.

In the past few years, NWO has already been investing in capacity building at the institutional level, mainly through calls to support digital competence centres: Local Digital Competence Centres (LDCCs)¹ and Thematic Digital Competence Centres (TDCCs). These calls have been primarily set up as a result of funding from the Implementation Plan Investments Digital Research Infrastructure². Investment in LDCCs allowed knowledge institutions to appoint data stewards and research software engineers. The three TDCCs have been set up at the national level in order to strengthen digital competencies by facilitating collaboration across individual knowledge institutions on issues that cut across institutional borders.

1.2 Available budget

The available budget for this Call for proposals is €15,000,000.00. Within this Call for proposals it is expected that a maximum of 27 proposals will be awarded funding.

There are three types of possible applications³:

- Type 1: for existing LDCCs;
- Type 2: for existing TDCCs;
- Type 3: for the Netherlands eScience Center.

This Call for proposals is not competitive and co-funding is not required.

1.3 Submission deadline(s)

The deadline for submitting full proposals is **25 June 2024**, before 14:00:00 CEST.

When you submit your application in ISAAC, you will also need to enter some details online. Therefore please start submitting your application at least one day before the deadline of this Call for proposals. Applications that are submitted after the deadline will not be taken into consideration.

¹ There are 23 Local Digital Competence Centres in the Netherlands. They are established at the following institutions: Erasmus University Rotterdam, Leiden University, Maastricht University, Radboud University, Tilburg University, TU Delft, TU Eindhoven, University of Amsterdam, University of Groningen, University of Twente, Utrecht University, VU Amsterdam, Wageningen University & Research, Amsterdam UMC, Erasmus MC, Leiden UMC, Maastricht UMC+, Radboud UMC, UMC Groningen, UMC Utrecht. There is one LDCC each for the KNAW Institutes, the NWO Institutes and the Universities of Applied Sciences.

² <https://www.nwo.nl/en/researchprogrammes/implementation-plan-investments-digital-research-infrastructure>

³ See chapter 7.1 for an explanation of the three types of applications.

2 Aim

This chapter describes the aim of the programme.

2.1 Aim of the programme

The aim of this Call for proposals is to strengthen the capacity of local and thematic DCCs. The professional capacity for effectively working with research software and data has been increased through the investment in building and expanding Local and Thematic Digital Competence Centres (LDCCs and TDCCs). However, two areas are still not adequately addressed: research software training and data interoperability. Increasing the capacity in these two areas is therefore the objective of this Call for proposals.

As research becomes increasingly reliant on computational methods, there is a need for a larger number of researchers with sufficient digital and computational expertise to make a maximum contribution to, and profit from, the use of open research software. To develop open, FAIR and sustainable software, best practices in software development, management, licensing and curation must be followed. Researchers are typically highly proficient in their own area of research, but usually lack formal qualifications or training in software development and management. There is therefore a demand for training of researchers in these two areas. However, there is a shortage of trainers to meet this demand, particularly when it comes to introductory and foundational skills.

The tools to share data in repositories and to create persistent links are now widely available. These tools help to address the ‘Findability’ and ‘Accessibility’ aspects of the FAIR principles. However, attention to the interoperability aspects is lagging behind. Without addressing all four of the FAIR principles, FAIR data cannot be truly ‘Reusable’: they cannot be integrated with other data and workflows for analysis, storage and processing (e.g. due to lack of metadata or incompatibility of file formats, but also due to incompatible or unclear licensing), but also represent a challenge in terms of their reuse by practitioners and other non-research stakeholders.

The EOSC FAIR Working Group’s FAIR in Practice Task Force indicated that funding community efforts is essential to improve the interoperability of research data⁴. The group recommended that communities should define and implement standards for the tools and workflows they use when working with data. Moreover, given that science crosses national borders, for the successful implementation of metadata standards and ontologies⁵, communities need to collaborate internationally and align their efforts with research infrastructures where data are produced, stored and shared.

The aim of this funding programme is to expand local and thematic DCCs with research software training capacity and expertise in ontology and/or metadata of research data (knowledge of metadata schemes and experience with ontologies and semantic modelling). The expanded software training capacity, brought together in a national network, will help increase the number of researchers and research support staff that can be trained in the area of open research software. The investment in ontology and metadata expertise will help address the data interoperability aspects of the FAIR principles.

⁴ Six Recommendations for implementation of FAIR practice by the FAIR in practice task force of [the European open science cloud FAIR working group](#).

⁵ An ontology is a way of showing the properties of a subject area and how they are related, by defining a set of terms and relational expressions that represent the entities in that subject area [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ontology_\(information_science\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ontology_(information_science)).

Applications are expected to outline adequate plans to sustain the additional capacity in the long-term.

3 Conditions for applicants

This chapter contains the conditions that are applicable to your grant application. Firstly it describes who can apply for funding (Section 3.1) and what you can request funding for (Section 3.2). Subsequently, you will find the conditions for preparing and submitting the application (Sections 3.3 and 3.4) and the specific funding conditions (Section 3.5).

3.1 Who can apply

Individuals acting on behalf of the board of the following organisations may submit an application:

- universities located in the Kingdom of the Netherlands;
- university medical centres;
- institutes affiliated to the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW) or NWO;
- the Health Research Infrastructure initiative (Health-RI);
- the Netherlands eScience Center (NLeSC);
- universities of applied sciences, as referred to in Article 1.8 of the Dutch Higher Education and Research Act (Wet op het hoger onderwijs en wetenschappelijk onderzoek, WHW).

Persons with a zero-hour employment agreement may not submit a proposal.

Additional conditions:

- For applications type 1, the organisation must already have an existing local DCC. This means that the following three organisations each apply as one local DCC: the KNAW institutes, the NWO institutes, and the universities of applied sciences.
- Type 1 applications have to be signed by the Executive Board of the organisation.
- A maximum of one type 1 and one type 2 application can be submitted per organisation.
- To ensure alignment with the activities of the Research Software Training NL network, the application type 3 is submitted by the Netherlands eScience Center.

3.2 What can be applied for

For an application in this Call for proposals, in total a maximum of €500,000.00 can be applied for in applications type 1 and type 3, and a maximum of € 1,000,000.00 in an application type 2.

Application type 1, exclusively for LDCCs

Each established LDCC can apply for maximum 0.5 FTE trainer capacity per year for open source software skills and maximum 0.5 FTE per year community manager capacity focusing on research data interoperability. The community managers will work closely with researchers and existing professionals (e.g. data librarians, data stewards) locally and connect them with metadata and ontology experts within TDCCs to improve interoperability aspects of research data.

Application type 2, exclusively for TDCCs

Each TDCC can make an application to increase its capacity in the area of domain-specific metadata and ontologies (max. 2 FTE per year) to support the local communities with the implementation of domain- and discipline-specific standards and tools, and to connect them with infrastructures and service providers. A crucial aspect of this is to also facilitate international alignment. The appointed personnel must have content expertise in the area of metadata and/or ontologies. However, within the maximum capacity allowed, it is also possible to appoint supporting roles, for example community managers, project coordinators or trainers. It needs to be explained in the application how the composition of the appointed personnel helps to achieve the overarching goal of the project.

Application type 3, exclusively for the Netherlands eScience Center

The Netherlands eScience Center can apply to appoint up to 1 FTE community management capacity per year to bring together the software trainers appointed at the LDCCs in a national network. This programme is expected to include train-the-trainer activities, as well as collaboration on open training material development in alignment with the activities of Research Software Training NL⁶.

The maximum duration of the proposed project is 4 years. The budget modules (including the maximum amount) available for this Call for proposals are listed in the table below. Apply only for funding that is vital to realise the project. A more detailed explanation of the budget modules can be found in the annex to this Call for proposals (7.2).

Budget module	Maximum amount
Non-scientific staff (NSS) at universities	Max 1 FTE total per year for 4 years (maximum €450,000.00) for type 1 applications, and max. 2 FTE total per year for 4 years (maximum €900,000.00) for type 2 applications, in accordance with the applicable rate at the time of submitting the application as taken from Table 2.2, column ‘Hourly rate productive hours, excl. Dutch VAT’ from the Handleiding Overheidstarieven [HOT- Manual Dutch Government rates] (Salary tables NWO). If the application is granted, the actual award will be made in accordance with the rates applicable at the time of the funding decision.
Personnel at universities of applied sciences, educational institutions and other organisations	Max 1 FTE total per year for 4 years (maximum €450,000.00) for type 1 applications and type 3 applications, and max. 2 FTE total per year for 4 years (maximum €900,000.00) for type 2 applications, in accordance with the applicable rate at the time of submitting the application as taken from Table 2.2, column ‘Hourly rate productive hours, excl. Dutch VAT’ from the Handleiding Overheidstarieven [HOT- Manual Dutch Government rates] (Salary tables NWO). If the application is granted, the actual award will be made in accordance with the rates applicable at the time of the funding decision.

⁶ Research Software Training NL is a network that brings together and facilitates training organisations in the Netherlands in the areas of research software, programming skills, applied data science, computational skills and open source: <https://researchsoftwaretraining.nl/>.

Budget module	Maximum amount
Material costs	€15,000 per year per FTE

3.3 Preparing an application

The steps involved in writing your application are:

- download the application form from the NWO web application ISAAC or from the NWO web page (on the grant page of the funding instrument concerned);
- complete the application form;
- save the application form in ISAAC as a PDF file and upload it with any compulsory annexes;
- fill in the requested information online in ISAAC.

Compulsory annexes:

- budget;
- For application type 2: declaration of support from the TDCC⁷ governing body (if in place) or the network manager (if the governing body is not yet in place). The letter must confirm the support for the proposal to appoint the metadata and ontology experts for their TDCC at the applicant's institution.

The appendix must be drawn up in accordance with the template provided by NWO. Annexes must be uploaded in ISAAC separately from the application. The budget must be submitted in ISAAC as an Excel file. All of the other annexes, except for the budget, must be submitted as PDF files (without encryption). Any annexes other than those stated above are not permitted.

You must write your application in English.

An application can only be submitted via the web application ISAAC. Applications that are not submitted via ISAAC will not be taken into consideration.

As the main applicant, you are required to submit the application via your own personal ISAAC account.

It is important to start with your application in ISAAC on time:

- if you do not yet have an ISAAC account, then you should create this on time to prevent any possible registration problems;
- any new organisations must also be added to ISAAC by NWO;
- you also need to submit other details online.

Applications submitted after the deadline will not be taken into consideration by NWO. For technical questions, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk, see contact (Chapter 6).

⁷ TDCCs are the three domain specific TDCCs established by NWO as a result of funding from the Implementation Plan Investments Digital Research Infrastructure: <https://www.nwo.nl/en/researchprogrammes/implementation-plan-investments-digital-research-infrastructure>

Does a main and/or co-applicant work at an organisation that is not included in the ISAAC database? You can report this via relatiebeheer@nwo.nl so that the organisation can be added. This will take several days. It is therefore important that you report this at least one week before the deadline.

Applicants are expected to have informed the organization where they work about submitting the application and that the organisation accepts the grant conditions of this Call for proposals.

3.4 Conditions for submission

3.4.1 Formal conditions for submission

NWO will assess your application against the conditions listed below. Your application will only be admitted to the assessment procedure if it meets these conditions. After submitting your application, NWO requests you to be available to implement any possible administrative corrections so that you can (still) meet the conditions for submission.

These conditions are:

- the main applicant meets the conditions stated in Section 3.1;
- the application complies with the DORA guidelines as described in Section 4.1;
- the application form is, after a possible request to make additions or changes, complete and filled out according to the instructions;
- the application is submitted via the main applicant's ISAAC account;
- the application is received before the deadline;
- the application is written in English;
- the application budget is drawn up in accordance with the conditions for this Call for proposals;
- the proposed project has a duration of at most 4 years;
- all of the required annexes are, after a possible request to make additions or changes, complete and filled out according to the instructions.

3.5 Conditions on granting

The [NWO Grant Rules 2017](#) are applicable to all applications.

3.5.1 Compliance with the National Knowledge Security Guidelines

World-class science can benefit from international cooperation. The National Knowledge Security Guidelines (hereafter: the Guidelines) helps knowledge institutions to ensure that international cooperation can take place securely. Knowledge security concerns the undesirable transfer of sensitive knowledge and technology that compromises national security; the covert influence of state actors on education and research, which jeopardises academic freedom and social safety; and ethical issues that may arise in cooperation with countries that do not respect fundamental rights.

Applicants are responsible for ensuring that their project complies and will continue to comply with the Guidelines. By submitting an application, the applicant commits to the recommendations stipulated in these Guidelines. In the event of a suspected breach of the Guidelines in an application submitted to NWO for project funding, or in a project funded by NWO, NWO may ask the applicant to provide a risk assessment demonstrating that the recommendations in the Guidelines have been taken into consideration. If the applicant fails to comply with NWO's request, or if the risk assessment is in apparent breach of the Guidelines, this may affect NWO's grant award or decision-making process. NWO may also include further conditions in the award letter if appropriate.

The National Knowledge Security Guidelines can be found on the central government website at: [Home | National Contact Point for Knowledge Security \(loketkennisveiligheid.nl\)](#).

3.5.2 Scientific integrity

In accordance with the NWO Grant Rules 2017, the project that NWO funds must be carried out in accordance with the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (2018). By submitting the proposal, the applicant commits to this code. In the case of a (possible) violation of these standards during a project funded by NWO, the applicant should immediately inform NWO of this and should submit all relevant documents to NWO. More information about the code of conduct and the policy regarding research integrity can be found on the website: [Scientific integrity | NWO](#).

3.5.3 Ethical statement or licence

The applicant is responsible for determining whether an ethical statement or licence is needed for the realisation of the proposed project. The applicant should ensure that this is obtained from the relevant institution or ethics committee on time. The absence or presence of an ethical statement or licence at the time of the application process has no effect on the assessment of the application. If the project is awarded funding, then the grant is issued under the condition that the necessary ethical statement or licence is obtained before the latest start date for the project. The project cannot start until NWO has received a copy of the ethical statement or licence.

3.5.4 Nagoya Protocol

The Nagoya Protocol ensures an honest and reasonable distribution of benefits emerging from the use of genetic resources (Access and Benefit Sharing; ABS). Researchers who make use of genetic sources from the Netherlands or abroad for their research should familiarise themselves with the Nagoya Protocol (ABS Focal Point - ABS Focal Point). NWO assumes that researchers will take all necessary actions with respect to the Nagoya Protocol.

4 Assessment procedure

This chapter first describes the assessment according to the DORA principles (Section 4.1) and the course of the assessment procedure (Section 4.2). Second, it states the criteria that the assessment committee will use to assess your application (Section 4.3).

The NWO Code for Dealing with Personal Interests applies to all persons and NWO employees involved in the assessment and/or decision-making process ([Code for Dealing with Personal Interests | NWO](#)).

NWO strives to achieve an inclusive culture where there is no place for conscious or unconscious barriers due to cultural, ethnic or religious background, gender, sexual orientation, health or age ([Diversity and inclusion | NWO](#)). NWO encourages members of an assessment committee to be actively aware of implicit associations and to try to minimise these. NWO will provide them with information about concrete ways of improving the assessment of an application.

4.1 The San Francisco Declaration (DORA)

NWO is a signatory to the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA). DORA is a worldwide initiative that aims to improve the way research and researchers are assessed. DORA contains recommendations for research funders, research institutions, scientific journals and other parties.

DORA aims to reduce the uncritical use of bibliometric indicators and obviate unconscious bias in the assessment of research and researchers. DORA's overarching philosophy is that research should be evaluated on its own merits rather than on the basis of surrogate measures, such as the journal in which the research is published.

When assessing the scientific track record of applicants, NWO makes use of a broad definition of scientific output.

NWO requests committee members not to rely on indicators such as the Journal Impact Factor or the h-index when assessing applications. Applicants are not allowed to mention these in their applications. You are, however, allowed to list other scientific products besides publications, such as datasets, patents, software and code, et cetera.

For more information on how NWO is implementing the principles of DORA, see [DORA | NWO](#).

4.2 Procedure

The application procedure consists of the following steps:

- submission of the proposal;
- admissibility of the proposal;
- initial advice from the assessment committee;
- rebuttal;
- assessment committee meeting;
- decision-making.

An external, independent assessment committee will be assigned for this Call for proposals, consisting of representatives from science and practice with knowledge of the field. The task of the assessment committee is to assess the applications and the relevant documents that are submitted, in conjunction with each other and with regard to both the respective merits of each application and the assessment criteria outlined in this Call for proposals.

Due to the expertise present in the assessment committee, NWO has decided with regard to the assessment of these applications to exercise the option outlined in Article 2.2.4, paragraph 2, of the NWO Grant Rules 2017, to assess all applications without involving referees.

4.2.1 Submission of a proposal

For the submission of the proposal, a standard form is available on the funding page of this Call for proposals on the NWO website. When you write your proposal, you must adhere to the questions stated on this form and the procedure given in the explanatory notes. You must also adhere to the conditions for the maximum number of words and pages.

Your complete application form must have been received before the deadline via ISAAC (see Section 1.3). After this deadline, you can no longer submit a proposal. After submitting the proposal, the main applicant will receive a confirmation of receipt.

4.2.2 Admissibility of the proposal

As soon as possible after you have submitted your proposal, you will hear from NWO whether or not your proposal will be taken into consideration. NWO will determine this based on several administrative-technical criteria (see the formal conditions for submission, Section 3.4). NWO can only take your proposal into consideration if it meets these conditions.

Please bear in mind that within two weeks after the submission deadline, NWO may approach you with any possible administrative corrections that need to be made so that your proposal can (still) meet the conditions for submission. You will be given one opportunity to make the corrections, and you will be given five working days to do this.

4.2.3 Pre-advice assessment committee

After this, your proposal will be submitted for comments to several members of the assessment committee (the pre-advisers). The pre-advisers will provide a written substantive and reasoned response to the proposal. They will formulate these comments based on the substantive assessment criteria (see Section 4.3.1) and will give the proposal a numerical score per assessment criterion. For this, the NWO score table will be used (on a scale of 1 to 9, where “1” is excellent and “9” unsatisfactory).

4.2.4 Rebuttal

The main applicant subsequently receives the anonymised pre-advice. You then have the opportunity to formulate a rebuttal. You will be given five working days to submit your rebuttal via ISAAC. If you decide to withdraw the proposal, then you should do this as quickly as possible by sending an email stating this to the office and withdrawing the proposal in ISAAC. If NWO receives your rebuttal after the deadline, then it will not be included in the rest of the procedure.

4.2.5 Meeting of the assessment committee

The committee will make its own assessment based on the available material. Although the pre-advice will ‘guide’ the final assessment to a large extent, it will not be blindly accepted without question by the committee. The committee will consider and compare the arguments of the pre-advisers (also amongst each other) and examine whether the rebuttal contains a well-formulated response to the critical comments from the pre-advisers.

Following the discussion, the committee draws up a written recommendation addressed to the Open Science NL Steering Board about the quality and ranking of the proposals. This recommendation is based on the assessment criteria. The proposal must receive an overall qualification of at least “good” to be eligible for funding. The proposal must also receive at least the qualification “good” for each of the individual assessment criteria.

For more information about the qualifications, see [Applying for funding, how does it work? | NWO](#).

4.2.6 Decision-making

Finally, the Open Science NL Steering Board will assess the procedure followed as well as the advice from the assessment committee. They will subsequently determine the final qualifications and make a decision over awarding or rejecting the proposals.

4.2.7 Timetable

Below, you will find the timetable for this Call for proposals. During the current procedure, NWO might find it necessary to make further changes to the timetable for this Call for proposals. You will be informed about this in time.

Proposals	
25 June 2024 before 14:00 CEST	Deadline proposals
July/August 2024	Pre-advisers consulted
September 2024	Applicants can submit a rebuttal
September/October 2024	Assessment committee meeting
November/December 2024	Decision by the Open Science NL Steering Board

4.3 Criteria

4.3.1 Substantive assessment criteria

The applications submitted within this Call for proposals will be substantially assessed on the basis of the following criteria:

For application type 1 (LDCCs):

1. Alignment with the scope of the call (30%):

- a. To what extent does the proposed project fit within the scope of the programme, as described in Sections 2 and 3.2 of this Call for proposals?
2. Feasibility of the proposal (50%):
 - a. Are the plans for increasing research software training capacity clear and realistic?
 - b. Are the plans for increasing the capacity in the area of interoperability of research data clear and realistic?
 - c. Is there an analysis of risk factors and an adequate risk mitigation strategy?
 - d. Is the budget reasonable for the proposed work and sufficiently substantiated?
 3. Sustainability plans (20%):
 - a. Are the plans for long-term sustainability appropriate and sufficiently realistic?

For application type 2 (TDCCs):

1. Alignment with the scope of the call (30%):
 - a. To what extent does the proposed project fit within the scope of the programme, as described in Sections 2 and 3.2 of this Call for proposals?
2. Feasibility of the proposal (50%):
 - a. Are the plans for collaborating with community managers for research data interoperability appointed at local DCCs clear and realistic?
 - b. Are the plans for connecting with the relevant infrastructures, services, networks and other bodies nationally and internationally clear and realistic?
 - c. Is there an analysis of risk factors and an adequate risk mitigation strategy?
 - d. Is the budget reasonable for the proposed work and sufficiently substantiated?
3. Sustainability plans (20%):
 - a. Are the plans for long-term sustainability appropriate and sufficiently realistic?

For application type 3 (the Netherlands eScience Center):

1. Alignment with the scope of the call (30%)
 - a. To what extent does the proposed project fit within the scope of the programme, as described in Sections 2 and 3.2 of this Call for proposals?
2. Feasibility of the proposal (50%)
 - a. Are the plans to bring together the software trainers into a national network clear and realistic?
 - b. Are the plans for aligning the activities with those of Research Software Training NL and other relevant national and international initiatives clear and realistic?
 - c. Is there an analysis of risk factors and an adequate risk mitigation strategy?
 - d. Is the budget reasonable for the proposed work and sufficiently substantiated?
3. Sustainability plans (20%)
 - a. Are the plans for long-term sustainability appropriate and sufficiently realistic?

5 Obligations for grant recipients

This chapter details the various obligations that - in addition to the conditions stated in Section 3.5 - apply after funds have been awarded.

5.1.1 Intellectual property

With respect to intellectual property (IP), the NWO IP policy applies. This can be found in Chapter 4 of the NWO Grant Rules 2017.

Applicants must carry out a project funded by NWO during the time that they work for the knowledge institution. If an applicant or a researcher funded by NWO is appointed by more than one employer, then the other employer should relinquish any possible IP rights that emerge from the project of the applicant.

The model agreement that NWO makes available must be used and can be found on the funding page of this Call for proposals. This model agreement has been drawn up in accordance with the NWO Grant Rules 2017.

5.1.2 Socially responsible licensing

The knowledge that emerges from the project could be suitable for use in society. When agreements about licensing and/or the transfer of research results developed under this Call for proposals are made, due consideration should be given to the ten principles for socially responsible licensing, as stated in the NFU factsheet “19.4511_Ten_principles_for_Socially_Responsible_Licensing_v19-12-2019.pdf (nfu.nl)”.

5.1.3 Open Access

As a signatory to the Berlin Declaration (2003) and a member of cOAlition S (2018), NWO is committed to making the results of the research it funds openly accessible (Open Access). By doing this, NWO supports the ambitions of the Dutch government to make all publicly funded research available Open Access. Scientific publications arising from projects awarded on the basis of this Call for proposals must therefore be made available in Open Access form in accordance with the NWO Open Access Policy. For more detailed information about NWO's Open Access policy, see [Open Science | NWO](#).

Other outputs resulting from this Call for Proposals should also be shared as openly as possible, under an open licence. Examples of such outputs include presentations, reports, training materials, working papers and posters. It is advised that these outputs are shared via a trusted repository, such as the Zenodo platform which offers free storage.

6 Contact and other information

6.1 Contact

6.1.1 Specific questions

For administrative and procedural questions about this Call for proposals, please contact:

Dr. Mark van Assem
Tel nr. +31(0)70 344 0915
Email: dccversterken@nwo.nl

For content-related questions about this Call for proposals, please contact:

Dr. Maria Cruz (open research software)
Tel nr. +31(0)70 349 4208
Email: dccversterken@nwo.nl

Dr. Marta Teperek (FAIR data)
Tel nr. +31(0)70 349 4282
Email: dccversterken@nwo.nl

6.1.2 Technical questions about the web application ISAAC

For technical questions about the use of ISAAC, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk. Please read the manual first before consulting the helpdesk. The ISAAC helpdesk can be contacted from Monday to Friday between 10:00 and 17:00 hours on +31 (0)70 34 40 600. However, you can also submit your question by email to isaac.helpdesk@nwo.nl. You will then receive an answer within two working days.

6.2 Other information

The whole text of this Call for proposals has been published in both Dutch and English. The Dutch version is deemed authentic. For legal interpretation the text of the Dutch version will be decisive.

NWO processes data from applicants received in the context of this Call in accordance with the NWO Privacy Statement, [Privacy Statement | NWO](#).

NWO might approach applicants for an evaluation of the procedure and/or research programme.

7 Annexes

7.1 Explanation of the types of applications

There are three types of possible applications:

- Type 1, exclusively for LDCCs;
- Type 2, exclusively for TDCCs;
- Type 3, exclusively for the Netherlands eScience Center.

Application type 1, exclusively for LDCCs

Each established LDCC can apply for maximum 0.5 FTE trainer capacity per year for open source software skills and maximum 0.5 FTE per year community manager capacity focusing on interoperability. The community managers will work closely with researchers and existing professionals (e.g. data librarians, data stewards) locally and connect them with metadata and ontology experts within TDCCs to improve interoperability aspects of research data.

Additional conditions for applications type 1:

- Maximum € 500.000 can be requested per application. The costs are split into:
 - Personnel costs: max. 1 FTE total per year for 4 years (maximum €450,000.00) in accordance with the applicable rates at the time of submitting the application as taken from Table 2.2, column 'Hourly rate productive hours, excl. Dutch VAT' from the Handleiding Overheidstarieven [HOT- Manual Dutch Government rates] (Salary tables | NWO).
 - Material costs: max. €15,000 per year per FTE.
- The organisation must already have an existing local DCC. This means that the following three organisations each apply as one local DCC: the KNAW institutes, the NWO institutes, and the universities of applied sciences.
- The application has to be signed by the Executive Board of the organisation.
- A maximum of one type 1 application can be submitted per organisation.

Application type 2, exclusively for TDCCs

Each TDCC can make an application to increase its capacity in the area of domain-specific metadata and ontologies (max. 2 FTE per year) to support the local communities with the implementation of domain- and discipline-specific standards and tools, and to connect them with infrastructures and service providers. A crucial aspect of this is to also facilitate international alignment. The appointed personnel must have content expertise in the area of metadata and/of ontologies. However, within the maximum capacity allowed, it is also possible to appoint supporting roles, for example community managers, project coordinators or trainers. It has to be explained in the application how the composition of the appointed personnel helps to achieve the overarching goal of the project.

Additional conditions for applications type 2:

- Maximum € 1,000,000.00 can be requested per application. The costs are split into:
 - Personnel costs: max. 2 FTE total per year for 4 years (maximum €900,000.00) in accordance with the applicable rates at the time of submitting the application as taken from Table 2.2, column 'Hourly rate productive hours, excl. Dutch VAT' from the Handleiding Overheidstarieven [HOT- Manual Dutch Government rates] (Salary tables | NWO).

- Material costs: max. €15,000 per year per FTE.
- A maximum of one type 2 application can be submitted per organisation.
- The application must be accompanied by a declaration of support from the TDCC governing body (if in place) or the network manager (if the governing body is not yet in place). The letter must confirm the support for the proposal to appoint the metadata and ontology experts for their TDCC at the applicant's institution.

Application type 3, exclusively for the Netherlands eScience Center

The Netherlands eScience Center can apply to appoint up to 1 FTE community management capacity per year to bring together the software trainers appointed at the LDCCs in a national network. This programme is expected to include train-the-trainer activities, as well as collaboration on open training material development in alignment with the activities of Research Software Training NL⁸.

Additional conditions for applications type 3:

- Maximum € 500,000.00 can be requested per application. The costs are split into:
 - Personnel costs: max. 1 FTE total per year for 4 years (maximum €450,000.00) in accordance with the applicable rates at the time of submitting the application as taken from Table 2.2, column 'Hourly rate productive hours, excl. Dutch VAT' from the *Handleiding Overheidstarieven* [HOT- Manual Dutch Government rates] (Salary tables | NWO).
 - Material costs: max. €15,000 per year per FTE.
- To ensure alignment with the activities of the Research Software Training NL network, the application type 3 is submitted by the Netherlands eScience Center.

7.2 Explanation of budget modules

It is possible to apply for the funding of the salary costs of personnel who make a substantial contribution to the project. Funding of these salary costs depends on the type of appointment and the organisation where the personnel are/ will be appointed.

- For university and university medical centres appointments, as well as for personnel from universities of applied sciences, educational institutions and other organisations, the salary costs are funded based on the collective labour agreement pay scale of the employee concerned in accordance with the applicable rate at the time of submitting the grant as taken from Table 2.2, column 'Hourly rate productive hours, excl. Dutch VAT' from the *Handleiding Overheidstarieven* [HOT- Manual Dutch Government Rates] ([Salary tables | NWO](#)).

NWO will apply a mandatory one-off indexing of the salary⁹ costs with respect to:

- HOT rates: for proposals submitted before 1 January that are awarded funding after 1 January.

⁸ Research Software Training NL network: <https://researchsoftwaretraining.nl/>

⁹ 1 July, 1 August and 1 January are the dates on which the relevant rates are generally adjusted, in the case of indexation the date of actual annual adjustment will be taken into account.

The mandatory one-off indexing does not affect the level of the grant ceiling or the maximum amount of the grant awarded for each proposal. Both the level of the grant ceiling and the maximum amount of the grant awarded will remain unchanged during the assessment procedure. The mandatory one-off indexing will be applied after the decision-making process about awarding or rejecting proposals is completed.

The available budget modules are explained below.

Personnel at universities, university medical centres, universities of applied sciences, educational institutions and other organisations

Costs for the funding of personnel employed at a university, university medical centre, university of applied sciences, educational institution or at other organisations will be remunerated in accordance with Table 2.2, column 'Hourly rate productive hours, excl. Dutch VAT' from the *Handleiding Overheidstarieven* [HOT- Manual Dutch Government Rates] ([Salary tables | NWO](#)).

For the calculation you should use the number of productive hours stated in the valid volume of the *Handleiding Overheidstarieven*.

Explanation of budget module Material

For each FTE applied for, a maximum of €15,000 material budget can be applied for per year of the appointment. Material budget for smaller appointments can be applied for on a proportionate basis and will be made available by NWO accordingly.

The applicant is responsible for distributing the total amount of material budget across the NWO-funded personnel positions. The material budget that can be applied for is specified according to the three categories below:

Project-related goods/services

- consumables (e.g. glassware, chemicals, cryogenic fluids, etc.);
- measurement and calculation time (e.g. access to supercomputer, etc.);
- costs for acquiring or using data collections (e.g. from Statistics Netherlands [CBS]), for which the total amount may not be more than €25,000 per proposal;
- access to large national and international facilities (e.g. cleanroom, synchrotron, etc.);
- work by third parties (e.g. laboratory analyses, data collection, citizen science, etc.);
- personnel costs for the appointment of a postdoc and/or non-scientific personnel for a smaller appointment size than those offered in the personnel budget modules.

Travel and accommodation costs for the personnel positions applied for

- travel and accommodation costs;
- conference attendance (maximum of two per year per scientific position applied for);
- fieldwork;
- work visit.

Implementation costs

- national symposium/conference/workshop organised by the project researchers;
- costs for Open Access publishing (solely in full gold Open Access journals, registered in the "Directory of Open Access Journals" <https://doaj.org/>);
- costs data management;
- costs involved in applying for licences (e.g. for animal experiments);
- audit costs (only for institutions that are not subject to the education accountants protocol of the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science), maximum €5,000 per proposal; for projects with a duration of three years or less, a maximum of €2,500 per proposal applies.

Costs that cannot be applied for are:

- basic facilities within the institution (e.g. laptops, office furniture, etc.);
- maintenance and insurance costs.

If the maximum amount is not sufficient for realising the research, then this amount may be deviated from, if a clear justification is provided in the proposal.

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Visiting address:
Location The Hague
Laan van Nieuw Oost-Indië 300
2593 CE The Hague
The Netherlands

Location Utrecht
Winthontlaan 2
3526 KV Utrecht
The Netherlands

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